

ORGANIZING INTEGRATED LESSONS IN PRIMARY CLASSES ON THE BASE OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

Kamolova Mohichehra Azamat Qizi

Student of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: This article describes the organization of integrated lessons in elementary grades, the essence of integration and increasing the effectiveness of integrated lessons, and the organization of lessons based on modern educational technologies.

Key words: Integration, primary class, communication, natural and concrete sciences, students, educational technologies.

Nowadays, it is important to connect lessons in primary classes, to organize integrated lessons, to increase the effectiveness of lessons. This allows pedagogues to acquire deep knowledge and skills, creativity and inquisitiveness, to be able to use modern educational technologies, and to organize non-traditional lessons. requires doing. Previously, lessons were traditionally organized through educational methods and didactic games, now there is a demand to organize lessons in a connected manner and to organize interesting methods and didactic games in integrated lessons through computer technologies and multimedia applications. First of all, it is necessary to understand the essence of the content of integration.

The word "integration" comes from the Latin word *integratio* - restoration, filling, "integer" - whole. In this regard, we have two concepts: System, a concept that expresses the state of dependence of separate differentiated parts and tasks of the organism, and the process leading to this state. Differentiation is French (differentiation, Latin *differentia* - difference, variety), that is, to divide the whole into parts, to separate. Integrating educational content is a world tradition (idea, thought, aspiration). An integrative approach reflects the objective integrity of systemic relations at different levels (nature - society - man). Integration is about

bringing together previously separated parts into a whole. It leads to an increase in the level of integrity and organization of the elements of the system, during integration, the volume of interdependence increases and decreases, the functioning of the system parts and the integrity of the learning object are regulated. How can these general principles be applied in schooling? According to the modern didactics and methodology, the success of teaching, development and upbringing of students is the formation of the concept of the unity of the world in them, their understanding of the need to guide their activities based on the general laws of nature, and the ability to resolve inter- and intra-discipline connections in the course of natural science. related to Integration in education is considered through a systematic approach to the construction of the content of educational subjects. Different levels of integration are distinguished: elementary, elements about nature, combining knowledge; intermediate - integration of divisions of subjects; final - integration of the last stage of education related to the study of science. At the same time, the possibility of fuller and wider integration of natural science education is not denied. As a psychological basis of the process of integration of school education, psychologist Y.A. Samarin's ideas about associative thinking can be taken. The essence of these thoughts is that any knowledge is an analogy, and a system of knowledge is a system of analogies. Y.A. Samarin distinguishes the following types of similes:

- local (local, limited to a certain place, thing); - belonging to a system; - within the system; - between systems; - classifies the levels of mental activity according to the nature of combining them with the corresponding level of analogy. The simplest of the connections that form the simplest knowledge about nature or an object is a local imagination limited to a certain place or concept. This connection is relatively isolated from other knowledge, so it provides the simplest mental activity. This is typical of junior high school age. Concepts that belong to a system are the simplest system concepts. They are formed based on the study of a topic, subject or event.

Knowledge of a subject, the selection of new evidence and concepts is carried out by comparing them with knowledge. The simplest generalization of knowledge takes place. But it would be the same if the acquired knowledge is connected with the knowledge that is close to it. In this, the students' analysis and generalization activities are created. Concepts within the system ensure students' knowledge of the entire system of sciences (physical, chemical, biological knowledge system), extensive use of knowledge is observed within the scope of the studied science. It reflects imagination, time, environment, and number connections within the system. Intersubjective imagination is the highest level of mental activity. They combine different systems of knowledge, provide an opportunity to know the diversity of the phenomenon or process. Based on this knowledge, general concepts arise. The formation of intersystemic ideas allows them to use knowledge, to subordinate them to each other, to identify gaps in the boundaries of knowledge. The described psychological evidence allows to determine the main features of the integration of primary, incomplete middle and high school education. The educational process does not negate the integration system of subjects, improves the integration system, eliminates its shortcomings. Deepening the connections and connections between subjects, such approaches rely on an understanding of the relationship between differentiation and integration. The purpose of pedagogy is to integrate the elements and parts of different subjects with the same goals and tasks into a whole, and it is to help teachers in the implementation of integration. Experiences show that elementary school teachers, and later graduates, have difficulty applying this knowledge and skills to other subjects after learning one or another subject, and they are not able to think independently, apply the acquired knowledge. Lack of transferability skills to similar or new situations. All this is happening due to the inconsistency of training in different subjects in primary school. In this case, integration is not a process of transfer of knowledge from one subject to another and an exchange of activities, but a process of creating new didactic equivalents that reflect the directions of integration of modern sciences. Psychologist E.N. According

to Kabanova Miller, "The independent transfer of knowledge, skills and abilities to the teacher based on each task he has not encountered is an important indicator of mental development." If he focuses on the importance of integration of school education in his work "Experience of integration of education in primary grades", L.P. Eyenko believes that integration is a means of making the lesson more effective, a form of raising subject relationships to new levels. Integration - is a source of finding new evidence that confirms or deepens the observations and conclusions of teachers in various subjects. They prevent students from getting tired and nervous by alternating different forms of activity.

List of references:

- 1.Mavlonova R,Rahmonqulova N.,„Boshlang'ich ta'limning integratsiyalashgan pedagogikasi". Ōquv qōllanma.
2. Salohiddinova N.,„Boshlang'ich sinflarda integratsiyalashgan ta'limni takomillashtirish".Ōquv qōllanma.
3. Mavlonova R, Rahmonqulova N. „Boshlang'ich ta'lim pedagogikasi.Innovatsiya va integratsiya. Ōquv qōllanma.
4.1-2-3-sinf Matematika.Darslik.
5.1-2-3-sinf Tabiiy fan.Darslik.
6. R.Norqobilova, M.To'rayeva Importance of talent in child development. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, VOLUME 3, ISSUE 7,July. 2022 57-61.
7. R.D.Norqobilova, P.Nazarova. "Pedagogical Possibilities of education of young generation at Abu Rayhan Beruni teaching". Web of Scientific Research Journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 6, June 2022. 1908-1911.
8. R.D.Norqobilova, S.Xoliyeva. "Eastern Scientists Views on Speech". Web of Scientific Research Journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 6, June 2022. 1434-1437.
9. R.D.Norqobilova, S.Xoliyeva, M.Mamatmurodova. "The importance of people's oral creativity in the development of spech by primary school students".

European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements. <https://www.scholarzest.com> Vol.3 No.06, June 2022 2660-5589. 84-86

10. R.D.Norqobilova, S.Ibrohimova, M.Mamatmurodova. "Pedagogical and Psychological Factors of using the heritage of asian thinkers in the formation of ecological thinking in primary school science". European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements. <https://www.scholarzest.com> Vol.3 No.06, June 2022 2660-5589. 81-83

11. R.D.Norqobilova, S.K.Zoirova, B.M.Tajimirzayeva. "Nigh spiritual generation-third renaissance builders". Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. ISSN: 2249-7315 Vol.12, Issue 05, May 2022.

12. R.D.Norqobilova. "Pedagogical basis of interdisciplinary communication in the educational process". International Journal on orange technologies. www.journalsresearchparks.org/index.php/IJOT e-ISSN: 2615-140|p-ISSN:2615-7071 Volume: 02 Issue:10|OCT 2020. 108-111.

13. R.D.Norqobilova. "Determining and developing students' mother language ability as a social-pedagogical problem". JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal. Volume 8, Issue 10, Oct., 2022, Published by Novateur Publication, M.S. India. 7-10.

14. R.D.Norqobilova. "Indikatorlar asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari faoliyatini diagnostika qilishning o'ziga xosligi". Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali, 2022.

15. R.Norqobilova, S.Ibrohimova."Pedagogical and psychological factors of using the heritage of Asian thinkers in the formation of ecological thinking in primary school science classes". European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA). Available Online at: <https://www.scholarzest.com> .Vol. 3 No. 06, June 2022. ISSN: 2660-5589

16. R.D.Norqobilova. "Methods of improving the mechanisms of diagnosing the mother language ability of primary class students". The role of science and innovation in the modern world. 139-143. 2022

17. R.D.Norqobilova. "Methods of Forming Beautiful Writing Skills in Primary School Students". International Journal of Development and Public Policy. |e-ISSN: 2792-3991| www.openaccessjournals.eu| Volume: 1 Issue: 7 181-183.